

NEUTRON STAR REDSHIFTS

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ABSTRACT

Gravitational redshifts of neutron stars have a theoretical upper limit of $z=0.62$. Also, it is generally believed that neutron stars have magnetic fields in the range of 10^{12} - 10^{13} G. A previously predicted electromagnetic time dilation effect has been shown to correctly predict decay lifetimes of muons bound to atomic nuclei. In this paper it is shown that the electromagnetic time dilation effect, along with the gravitational time dilation effect, can produce total neutron star redshifts that are substantially larger than 0.62. For instance, z can reach 4.89 for $B \sim 1.25 \times 10^{13}$ G. Also, z can reach ∞ or cutoff at $B \sim 1.87 \times 10^{13}$. A redshift of $z=4.89$ requires a hydrogen atmosphere. A helium atmosphere should be much more common. For a helium atmosphere, $z \sim 2$ for $B \sim 10^{13}$ G. This is in good agreement with the observed scarcity of quasi-stellar objects with redshifts greater than about 2.

KEY WORDS: General relativity; Electromagnetic field; Neutron stars; Redshifts; Quasars

1. INTRODUCTION

It is generally believed that neutron stars have magnetic fields in the range of 10^{12} - 10^{13} G. Furthermore, we do not expect a gaseous atmosphere, but rather that at even almost zero vapor pressure the surface will condense to form a magnetic polymeric solid and that the density will rise from zero to about 10^4 g cm⁻³ within a Bohr radius[1--3]. A solid atmosphere is expected up to temperatures of about 10^8 °K.

If appropriate conditions on the equation of state and on stability are applied, it has been shown by Bondi[4] that gravitational redshifts have an upper limit of $z=0.62$. In a previous paper,[5] a reinterpretation of Maxwell-Einstein theory was shown to predict an electromagnetic time dilation effect analogous to the gravitational time dilation effect. The electromagnetic time dilation effect has been shown to correctly predict decay lifetimes of muons bound to atomic nuclei[6]. This effect has also been discussed at by Rodrigues, et. al.[7], Beil[8], and Krori, et. al.[9]. In the current paper it is shown that for a standard neutron star model the electromagnetic time dilation effect, along with the gravitational time dilation effect, can produce total redshifts that are substantially larger than 0.62. For instance, z can reach 4.89 for $B \sim 1.25 \times 10^{13}$ G [10,11]. Also, z can reach ∞ or cutoff at $B \sim 1.87 \times 10^{13}$. [16]

Consequently, our reinterpretation of Maxwell-Einstein theory leads to the prediction that neutron stars can have redshifts that are as large as the redshifts observed in quasi-stellar objects. This result is correct even if quasi-stellar objects are cosmological. However, the result raises the possibility that some quasi-stellar objects might be neutron stars. Smith[12] points out that “there is still a minority opinion that the redshifts are not

cosmological.” Hoyle, G. Burbidge, and Arp [13,14] argue that quasi-stellar objects are non-cosmological.

Another interesting result is that a redshift of 4.89 for $z \sim 1.25 \times 10^{13}$ G requires a hydrogen atmosphere. A helium atmosphere should be much more common. For a helium atmosphere, z can only reach about 2 for $B \sim 10^{13}$ G. This result is in good agreement with the observed scarcity of quasi-stellar objects with redshifts greater than about 2 [11,15].

2. REDSHIFTS

Let $g_{\mu\nu}$ and A_μ be the gravitational and electromagnetic potentials at the surface of a neutron star. From a previous paper [5], the proper time interval for a displacement dx^μ at the surface of the star is

$$\begin{aligned} d\tau &= \frac{1}{c} \left[(g_{\mu\nu} dx^\mu dx^\nu)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{\rho'}{\rho c^2} A_\mu dx^\mu \right] \\ &= \frac{1}{c} (g_{\mu\nu} dx^\mu dx^\nu)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{1}{\rho c^2} [\rho' A_4 - \frac{1}{c} \tilde{J} \cdot \tilde{A}] dt \end{aligned}$$

where ρ' is the scalar charge density, ρ is the scalar mass density, \tilde{J} is the 3-current density, c is the speed of light, and \tilde{A} is the 3 vector potential. For a first approximation it can be assumed that $\rho' A_4 = 0$, and that $g_{\mu\nu}$, ρ , \tilde{J} , and \tilde{A} are independent of time.

But $\frac{1}{2c} \tilde{J} \cdot \tilde{A}$ is the magnetic energy density. The magnetic energy density also has the

form $\frac{B^2}{8\pi}$, where B is the magnitude of the magnetic field. Thus, we can write

$$d\tau = \frac{1}{c} (g_{\mu\nu} d^\mu d^\nu)^{\frac{1}{2}} - \frac{B^2}{4\pi\rho c^2} dt$$

For an oscillator, at rest, emitting at the surface of a neutron star

$$\frac{\nu}{\nu_0} = (g_{44})^{\frac{1}{2}} - \frac{B^2}{4\pi\rho c^2}$$

where ν is the frequency observed at infinity and ν_0 is the proper frequency.

Consequently,

$$z \equiv \frac{\lambda - \lambda_0}{\lambda_0} = [(g_{44})^{\frac{1}{2}} - \frac{B^2}{4\pi\rho c^2}]^{-1} - 1.$$

Let us define the magnetic and gravitational redshifts as

$$z_m = (1 - \frac{B^2}{4\pi\rho c^2})^{-1} - 1$$

$$z_g = (g_{44})^{-\frac{1}{2}} - 1.$$

Then

$$(z + 1)^{-1} = (z_g + 1)^{-1} + (z_m + 1)^{-1} - 1.$$

For $z = 4.89$ and $z_g = 0.62$, we get $z_m = 0.82$. For our sun, $z_g \sim 10^{-6}$ and $z_m \sim 10^{-13}$

For matter with atomic number N , with

$$1 \ll \eta \equiv (\frac{B}{4.6 \times 10^9 N^3})^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

and with B in the range 10^{12} - 10^{13} G, the density has been estimated[1,2] to be

$$\rho \sim 10^6 (\frac{N}{26})^4 \eta^{\frac{12}{5}}.$$

Putting this with the expression for z , we can solve for B

$$B \sim N^{\frac{1}{2}} [6.7 \times 10^{10} \{(g_{44})^{\frac{1}{2}} - (z + 1)^{-1}\}]^{\frac{5}{4}}.$$

$$B \sim N^{\frac{1}{2}} \left[6.7 \times 10^{10} \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{z_g+1} - \frac{1}{z+1} \right) \right\}^{\frac{5}{4}} \right]$$

For $z = 4.89$, $z_g = 0.62$ and $N = 1$ we get $B \sim 1.25 \times 10^{13} \text{G}$.

For $z = \infty$, $z_g = 0.62$, and $N = 1$ we get $B \sim 1.87 \times 10^{13} \text{G}$, which supports our conclusion from a previous paper, Pulsars and Redshifts,[16] that the electromagnetic time dilation effect of a neutron star can account for the properties of pulsars.

A redshift of $z = 4.89$ for $B \sim 10^{13} \text{G}$ requires a hydrogen atmosphere. A helium atmosphere should be much more common. We can write

$$z \sim \left[(g_{44})^{\frac{1}{2}} - 1.5 \times 10^{-11} \left(\frac{B}{N^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right)^{\frac{4}{5}} \right]^{-1} - 1.$$

$$z \sim \left[\frac{1}{z_g+1} - 1.5 \times 10^{-11} \left(\frac{B}{N^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right)^{\frac{4}{5}} \right]^{-1} - 1$$

For $B = 1.0 \times 10^{13} \text{G}$, $z_g = 0.62$, and $N = 2$ we get $z \sim 2.00$. This result is in good agreement with the observed scarcity of quasi-stellar objects with redshifts greater than about 2[11,15].

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